

Polymerase Chain reaction (PCR) in Life Sciences

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Background

The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is a rapid, inexpensive and simple way of copying specific DNA fragments from minute quantities of source DNA material also called as "PEOPLE'S (P) CHOICE (C) REACTION" (R). It is a revolutionary method developed by Kary Mullis in the 1980s an American biochemist who won the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 1993 for his invention. Before the development of PCR, the methods used to amplify, or generate copies of, recombinant DNA fragments were time-consuming and labour-intensive. In contrast, a machine designed to carry out PCR reactions can complete many rounds of replication, producing billions of copies of a DNA fragment, in only a few hours. PCR is based on using the ability of DNA polymerase to synthesize new strand of DNA complementary to the offered template strand. Because DNA polymerase can add a nucleotide only onto a pre-existing 3'-OH group, it needs a primer to which it can add the first nucleotide. At the end of the PCR reaction, the specific sequence will be accumulated in billions of copies (amplicons). PCR is now a common and often indispensable technique used in medical laboratory and clinical laboratory research for a broad variety of applications including biomedical research and criminal forensics.

Before PCR is performed, DNA must be isolated from peripheral blood, hair follicles, cheek cells, or tissue samples. Isolated DNA is double stranded, meaning that there are two sequences of letters or nucleotide bases (A or adenine, G or guanine, C or cytosine, and T or thymine). The double stranded DNA is held together by complementary base pairings in that A binds to T, C binds to G makes the complementary strand of the molecule understood. So, TTAACGGGGCCCTTAAA.....TTTAAACCCGGGTTT

Principle

The target sequence of nucleic acid is denatured to single strands, primers specific for each target strand sequence are added, and DNA polymerase catalyzes the addition of deoxynucleotides to extend and produce new strands complementary to each of the target sequence strands (cycle 1). In cycle 2, both double-stranded products of cycle 1 are denatured and subsequently serve as targets for more primer annealing and extension by DNA polymerase. After 25 to 30 cycles, at least 10^7 copies of target DNA may be produced by means of this thermal cycling.

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Mechanism Of PCR

It is important to note that since the new strand extends beyond the target DNA, they will contain a region next to their 3'-end that is complementary to the other prime

- **Step I: Denaturation**

This step is the first regular cycling event and consists of heating the reaction chamber to 94–98 °C (201–208 °F) for 20–30 seconds. This causes DNA melting, or denaturation, of the double-stranded DNA template by breaking the hydrogen bonds between complementary bases, yielding two single-stranded DNA molecules.

- **Step II: Annealing**

In the next step, the reaction temperature is lowered to 50–65 °C (122–149 °F) for 20–40 seconds, allowing annealing of the primers to each of the single-stranded DNA templates. The primers are single-stranded sequences themselves, but are much shorter than the length of the target region, complementing only very short sequences at the 3' end of each strand.

- **Step III Extension/elongation:**

The temperature at this step depends on the DNA polymerase used the optimum activity temperature for the thermostable DNA polymerase of Taq (*Thermus aquaticus*) polymerase is approximately 75–80 °C (167–176 °F) though a temperature of 72 °C (162 °F) is commonly used with this enzyme. In this step, the DNA polymerase synthesizes a new DNA strand complementary to the DNA template strand by adding free dNTPs from the reaction mixture that is complementary to the template in the 5'-to-3' direction, condensing the 5'-phosphate group of the dNTPs with the 3'-hydroxy group at the end of the nascent (elongating) DNA strand. The precise time required for elongation depends both on the DNA

polymerase used and on the length of the DNA target region to amplify. As a rule, at their optimal temperature, most DNA polymerases polymerize a thousand bases per minute. Under optimal conditions at each extension/elongation step, the number of DNA target sequences is doubled. With each successive cycle, the original template strands plus all newly generated strands become template strands for the next round of elongation, leading to exponential (geometric) amplification of the specific DNA target region.

Components Of PCR

The PCR Reaction Components are as follows:

- Mg²⁺
- Water
- Primer
- dNTPs
- PCR Buffer
- DNA polymerase

Plateau effect

The term plateau effect is used to describe the attenuation of the normally exponential rate of product accumulation in PCR. The attenuation occurs during the late PCR cycles when the accumulation of product reaches 0.3 to 1 picomole. Depending on reaction conditions and thermal cycling, one or more of the following may influence when the plateau is reached:

- Depletion of substrates (dNTPs or primers)
- End-product inhibition (pyrophosphate, duplex DNA)
- Competition for reactants by nonspecific products or primer-dimer
- Reannealing of specific product at concentration above 0.8 M (may decrease the extension rate or processivity of Taq DNA polymerase or change branch-migration of product strands and displacement of primers)
- Incomplete denaturation/strand separation of product at high product concentration.

Fig 1: Overview of PCR

Applications

PCR has a broad range of applications, not only in basic research but also in the areas of medical diagnostics, forensics, and agriculture. Some examples of PCR applications include:

- **Genotyping**

PCR can be used to detect sequence variations in alleles in specific cells or organisms. Genotyping by PCR is also a fundamental aspect of genetic analyses of mutations in cancer and heredity. The primer sets are designed to flank regions of interest and assess genetic variations based on the presence or absence of an amplicon and/or its length.

- **PCR cloning**

PCR is widely used in cloning DNA fragments of interest, in a technique known as PCR cloning. In direct PCR cloning, the desired region of a DNA source (e.g., gDNA, cDNA, plasmid DNA) is amplified and inserted into specially designed compatible vectors. Alternatively, primers may be designed with additional nucleotides at their 5' end for further manipulation before insertion.

- **Methylation**

PCR can be employed to investigate locus-specific methylation. In a method called methylation-specific PCR (MSP), two primer pairs are designed to differentiate the methylation state of the locus of interest. Positive PCR amplification resulting from primer binding is used to determine the methylation state of the locus.

- **Mutagenesis**

One of the benefits of PCR cloning is the ability to introduce desired mutations into the gene of interest via cloning, for mutagenesis studies. In site-directed mutagenesis, PCR primers are designed to incorporate base substitutions, deletions, or insertions within a specific sequence. Primers are directed at a sequence that has already been cloned in a plasmid.

- **Sequencing**

PCR is a relatively simple approach for enriching template DNA for sequencing. High-fidelity PCR is highly recommended for preparation of sequencing templates, in order to maintain DNA sequence accuracy.

MERITS OF PCR

- Specific, highly sensitive technique
- Relatively very simple
- Purity of DNA preparation is not critical
- Even degraded DNA can be used
- Highly versatile technique
- Quantity of DNA required for PCR is low.

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